

Marketing Practices and Challenges of Handloom Based Micro-Enterprises in Assam

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Abstract : *Handloom micro-entrepreneurial activity in the informal sector plays an important role in local economic development. Assam, a state of NER, has the highest number of handloom workers (12.84 lakh) among all the states of India. Wide varieties of products, such as Mekhela-Chadar, Gamosa, Riha, and other traditional attires, have been produced by weavers using different types of yarn and designs. In the current liberalised and competitive environment, the appropriate combination of marketing mix strategies is vital for the development of the sector. The present paper intends to analyse the marketing practises and problems of handloom enterprises in Assam. The study is based on primary data collected from 312 micro-level handloom enterprises in Assam through a multi-stage sampling technique. The 4Ps of marketing mix strategies, such as product, price, place, and promotion, are used for conceptualization. Promotional variables, lack of customer awareness, challenges from competitors, supply-side bottlenecks, demand fluctuation, intervention by intermediaries, and a lack of product diversity are identified as major marketing challenges for handloom enterprise in Assam.*

Keywords : Handloom Enterprises, Marketing Mix, Principal Component Analysis.

Introduction

Rural non-farm activities and rural industrialization in the informal sector are important for rural economic diversification through employment creation, income generation, and the prevention of rural-to-urban labour migration

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(Saith, 1992; Hazarika & Goswami, 2014). As an informal sector, the handloom industry in India is based on a large number of artisanal skill-based enterprises that contributed 11.79 percent of total textile production in 2019–20 and employed 35.22 lakh handloom workers in the same year (Ministry of Textile, 2020). The sector is also important in terms of export earnings. Indian textile and handloom products are exported to more than 100 countries around the world, and in 2019–20, the export earnings of the handloom sector amounted to Rs. 2248.33 crore (Ministry of Textile, 2021a). The top five major export markets for Indian handloom products are the USA, UK, Spain, Italy, and Germany (HEPC, 2022).

In India, handloom activities take place mainly in Assam, West Bengal, Tamil Nadu, Manipur, Uttar Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh, Tripura, Odisha, Arunachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Telangana, Nagaland, and Meghalaya, and 93 percent of the handloom workforce belongs to these 13 states (Baruah & Saha, 2022). More than half (52.62 percent) of handloom workers in India belong to the North East Region (NER). Assam, a state of NER, has the highest number of handloom workers (12.84 lakh) among all the states of India (Ministry of Textile 2020). In Assam, the majority of production units in the handloom sector are micro-enterprises, where the majority of the workers are self-employed micro-entrepreneurs. The weavers in Assam produce diversified handloom products using different types of yarn like cotton, mulberry silk, muga silk, eri spun silk, etc. Assamese handloom products have high demand at the local, regional, national, and international levels. Weaving activity also occupies an important space in Assamese culture. The weavers in the state are preserving their traditional arts and skills and representing culture through their weaving fabrics and designs. The level of artistry and complexity accomplished in handloom fabrics is unmatched, and it cannot be mechanically reproduced on a large scale.

The elimination of trade restrictions in the textile sector on January 1, 2005, increased competition among emerging economies like China, India, Bangladesh, Vietnam, Sri Lanka, and others to increase their market share. As a consequence, the Indian handloom industry, which is part of the textile industry, faced intense competition (Bortamuly & Goswami, 2015). In order to be competitive, the handloom sector needs to adopt effective marketing strategies. In the current liberalised and competitive environment, the appropriate combination of marketing mix strategies is vital for the development of the sector.

The government of India has undertaken many marketing programmes for increasing sales and reviving the handloom industry. The comprehensive

marketing promotion programme, handloom export promotion, organisation of fairs and exhibitions, urban haats, and brand building (Handloom Mark, Geographical Indicators, and Indian Handloom Brand) have been launched by the Ministry of Textiles, Government of India. Many well-known handloom items, including Benarasi saris, Ikat tie-and-dye saris from Andhra Pradesh, Kanchipuram saris from Tamil Nadu, Muga silk fabrics from Assam, and Santipur saris from West Bengal, are in high demand both domestically and abroad.

While price strategies, production efficiency, and cost minimization are often studied in economics, for designing an effective marketing strategy, product design, product promotion, product mix, marketing channels, and marketing problems are also important. Thus, it is important to analyse different dimensions of marketing practises in the handloom sector. In these contexts, the objective of the present paper is to analyse the marketing strategies of handloom microenterprises in Assam with a view to suggesting appropriate policies.

Review of Literature

Many studies have emphasised the adoption of appropriate marketing strategies to prevent the decline of the handloom sector. A study (Modak, 2006) observed that good business practises and the best product quality are the key reasons behind the success of Fab India. A case study (Niranjana, Annapurna, Syamasundary, & Uzrama, 2006) in Andhra Pradesh found that Anokhi, Fab India, Desi, Dastkar Andhra Pradesh Marketing Association, and Rehwa are the successful marketing agencies for weavers. A study (Vinayagamoorthy, 2018) in Thanjavur, India, observed that product, price, and place-related strategies were moderately effective and promotion was an ineffective strategy for the development of the handloom industry. A study (Rai & Srivastava, 2015) observed that wholesale, retail, and institutional forms are the important marketing channels for the Banarasi handloom cluster. A study (Ismail & Velnampy 2013) found that product mix and distribution strategy have a positive impact on the performance of the handloom industry in Sri Lanka. A study (Ramana, Reddy, Kumar, & Sirisha, 2019) in the Gunter District of Andhra Pradesh observed that the price of handloom products was determined by the cost-based pricing approach. Direct marketing, advertising, personal selling, quality, and discounts are the preferred promotional strategies for handloom entrepreneurs. A study (Hmangaihzuali & Ramswamy, 2015) was carried out in the Thenzawl handloom cluster in Mizoram to analyse the product policies of handloom weavers. It is

observed that the entrepreneur produced diversified handloom products, but they were not suitable for national and international markets. It is suggested that handloom entrepreneurs need government support with respect to the development of products, improvising design, brand building, creating networking with NIFT and NID, and setting up a common facility centre for testing the quality of the products. A study (Vadakepat & Khateeb, 2012) in Kerala used the product concentration index and competitive profile matrix to analyse the present market realities of traditional handloom products. The competitive profile matrix shows that out of the four success variables (product quality, convenient pricing, innovative distribution, and product awareness), product quality is the major strength of handloom products. Many studies identify that marketing is a common problem for the handloom industry in India. Studies (Narzari, 2013; Nadh & Harshavardhan, 2013; Ramswamy, 2013; Kumar & Sulaiman, 2017) observed that lack of availability of market information, awareness about product features, quality standards, insufficient promotion, improper management of handloom logistics, the poor role of the government, high competition, slackness in demand, and change in fashion and design were identified as the major marketing challenges of the handloom industry in India in studies carried out in Assam, Mizoram, Kerala, and Tamil Nadu.

Methodology

Sources of Data and Sampling Technique

The study is based on primary data collected from 312 handloom-based micro-enterprises spread over four districts of Assam, namely Kamrup (R), Barpeta, Sivasagar, and Nalbari, from October 2021 to February 2022. The study used a multi-stage sampling method at the district, block, village, and enterprise levels. At the first stage, four districts of Assam were selected purposefully on the basis of the highest number of weavers as per the data obtained from the Handloom Weaver Information System, Office of the Development Commissioner (Handloom), Ministry of Textile, Government of India. In the second stage, two development blocks from each selected district were selected based on the highest number of weavers. At the third stage, eight villages (one village from each selected block) were selected from the eight selected blocks on the basis of the commercial concentration of handloom activities as per information collected from the District Handloom and Textile Department. At the last stage, before collecting data at the village level, lists of handloom enterprise owners were prepared after discussions with the head of the village, master weavers, and ward members. For operational purposes, a "handloom

entrepreneur is defined as an individual who owns an enterprise with a minimum of one operating loom and has completed at least one year of operation. From the prepared list of each chosen sample village, 50 percent of handloom entrepreneurs were selected randomly.

Analytical Framework of Marketing Mix

Marketing is a social and managerial process through which individuals and groups obtain what they require and desire by creating, offering, and exchanging products of value (Kotler & Keller, 2016). The marketing process begins with the identification of consumers' specific needs and concludes only when those needs are satisfied. Marketing operations involved a large number of activities, including product planning, pricing, branding, channels of distribution, personal selling, advertising, promotions, packaging, display, service policies, physical handling policies related to warehousing and transportation, and fact-finding analysis (Borden, 1964). These marketing activities are typically referred to as the marketing mix, which is comprised of the 4Ps (product, price, place, and promotion) of the marketing mix model (McCarthy and Perreault, 2002; Kotler & Keller, 2016). The paper examines the marketing decision regarding product, price, place, and promotion, i.e., the 4 Ps of marketing strategy, from the producer's point of view with the help of simple descriptive statistical tools.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

To identify the marketing problems of the sample handloom enterprises in Assam, the PCA is used. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test of sphericity are used to test sampling adequacy and correlation among the variables, respectively. The perceptions of handloom entrepreneurs about marketing problems are collected using a structured questionnaire with closed-ended options, in which respondents were asked to rank according to a five-point Likert scale ranging from most important to irrelevant. The most important marketing problem, according to the individual respondent, should be ranked highest, and the least important one should be ranked lowest.

Results and Discussions

Product Practices

Product variety, quality, design, features, brand name, packaging, etc. are important components of the product strategy of a firm (Kotler & Keller, 2016). The product mix combines all the product lines and items offered by a firm. A product line refers to a group of closely related product items that are distributed

through some channels to the same consumer groups (Krishnamacharyulu & Ramakrishnan, 2011). The diversity of handloom products in the sample enterprises is shown in Table-1. It is revealed that the handloom micro-enterprises produce 12 items, which are classified under four product lines: mekhela-chadar, gamosa, traditional attire, and other items.

The Mekhela-Chadar (MC) is a traditional fabric worn by Assamese women. It may be produced using different types of yarn like cotton, mulberry silk, muga silk, eri spun silk, etc. In the sample, Mekhela-Chadar is classified into four categories based on types of yarn, design, and the amount of labour used in its weaving process. The **Mekhela-Chadar (MC)-I** is made by using cotton yarn and a simple hand design. The MC-I is more common among the weavers because half of the sample enterprises are involved in producing this item of product. The price range of the product varies between Rs. 800 and Rs. 2200. It is mainly due to the variation of colour, quality, and design within this product. The **Mekhela-Chadar (MC) II** is a high-quality tusser silk fabric, and Jacquard machines are used for designing. The minimum price of the product is Rs. 6000, and the maximum is Rs.14000. The **Mekhela-Chadar (MC)-III** is also made of tusser silk yarn, but the design is moderate. The price range of the product lies between Rs.3500 and Rs. 5500. The price ranges of MC-II and MC-III are different due to only the cost of design being different between the products. Out of 312 sample enterprises, 54 are involved in producing MC-II and 78 are producing MC-III. The **Mekhela-Chadar (MC)-IV** is made of Muga silk yarn and is the most valuable handloom product in Assam. Muga silk is one of the rarest silks in the world, and it is produced within the geographical area of Assam. The production of Muga depends on many climate conditions, such as temperature, humidity, soil, rainfall, and terrain. Assamese Muga Silk also has a Geographical Indication (GI) tag. For producing Muga silk fabrics, a high amount of working capital is required. As handloom units in the sample are micro-level enterprises, only eight enterprises are involved in producing Muga mekhela-chadar. They sell the product for between Rs.25000 and Rs.35000.

Gamosa is the most prominent handloom product of the Assamese people, representing their culture and heritage. It is commonly used to honour people, and it is also used during cultural festivals and religious rituals. Assamese men and women use the gamosa in various ways, depending on the traditional or cultural occasion. It may be woven by using different natural fibres or yarns, such as cotton, muga silk, tusser silk, mulberry silk, etc. In the sample, gamosa is classified into three categories, such as gamosa I, II, and III, on the basis of the

Table 1: Product mix of sample handloom enterprise in Assam.

Product line	Product items	Descriptions	No. of Enterprises	Price range (in Rs)
Product line I Mekhela-chadar set	Mekhla-Chadar (MC)-I	Made by using cotton yarn 24 to 32 hours of labour employment for producing single set. Hand design	157	800-2200
	Mekhela-Chadar (MC)-II	Made by using tusser silk 56 to 64 hours of labour engagement for producing single set. Fine designing using Jacquard machine	54	6000-14,000
	Mekhela Chadar (MC)-III	Made by using tusser silk 24 to 32 mandays labour engagement for producing single set Moderate hand design	78	3500-5500
	Mekhela-Chadar (MC)-IV	48 to 56 hours of labour engaged for producing single set Fine designing using Jacquard machine	8	25000-35000
Product line II Gamosa	Gamosa-I	Made by using tusser silk 3 to 4 hours of labour engagement for producing a single piece Fine design using jacquard machine	34	900- 1200
	Gamosa -II	Made by using cotton 3 to 4 hours of labour engagement producing a single piece Fine hand design and jacquard machine design	203	110-550
	Gamosa - III	Made by using cotton 2 to 4 hours of labour engagement producing a single piece Moderate hand design	21	80-300
Product line III Other Traditional attire	Dhoti	Made by using cotton 12 to 15 hours of labour engagement producing a single piece No design	11	500-700
	Seleng Kapur	Made by using cotton / mulberry silk 7 to 10 hours of labour engagement producing a single piece Moderate hand design	14	400-1100
Product line IV Other items	Tangali	Made by using cotton or wool 3 to 5 hours of labour engagement producing a single piece Moderate hand design	2	400
	Shirt piece	Made by using cotton or muga silk 12 to 16 hours of labour engagement producing a single piece Hand design	3	1000 -2000
	Mufflar	Made by using cotton or wool 8 to 12 hours of labour engagement producing a single piece Moderate hand design	3	300-500

Source: Computed from primary data, 2021-22

types of yarn and techniques of design use. The Gamosa I is produced using tussler yarn, and the design is made with the help of a jacquard machine. In the sample enterprises, only 34 are producing Gamosa I, which they sell in the price range of Rs.900 – Rs.1200. Gamosa II and III are made by using cotton yarn, but the design is different between the two types. Gamosa II is made with either a fine hand design or a jacquard machine design. While moderate hand design is used for making Gamosa III. In the sample, the majority of enterprises (203) are producing Gamosa II and selling the product for a price between Rs.110 and Rs.550.

The dhoti and gamosa seem to be the traditional attire of the men of Assam. The dhoti is also a well-known garment in other Indian traditions and is used to cover the lower half of the body. In the sample, a few enterprises (11) are involved in producing dhoti, which is sold in the price range of Rs.500 to Rs.700.

Seleng Kapur (or chadar) is an important traditional attire for Assamese men and women. It is mainly used during traditional and religious festivals. In the sample, only 14 enterprises are involved in producing cheleng-chadar, which is produced only as per order. The price range of seleng chadar is Rs.400 – Rs.1100.

The other items, like tangali, shirt pieces, and mufflers, produced by other enterprises are limited in the sample. Among the sample enterprises, only 2 are producing tangali, 3 are producing shirt pieces, and 3 are producing mufflers. The enterprises only produce these three items in accordance with orders.

Table 2: Share of different products in total sales of sample enterprises during the survey year

Products Name	Estimated sales turnover (in lakhs)	Share in total sales turnover (in per cent)
Mekhela-Chadar-I	103.62	8.62
Mekhela-Chadar-II	419.25	34.89
Mekhela Chader-III	189.09	15.74
Mekhela-Chadar-IV	24.90	2.07
Gamosa -I	198.78	16.54
Gamosa-II	233.31	19.42
Gamosa-III	9.54	0.79
Dhoti	0.43	0.04
Cheleng Kapur	13.26	1.10
Shirt	0.60	0.05
Muffler & Tungali	8.79	0.73
Total	1201.56	100.00

Source: Computed from primary data, 2021-22

Table-2 shows the share of the sales value of different handloom products in the total sales turnover of sample enterprises in Assam during the survey year. It is observed that the total sales turnover of the sample enterprises is Rs. 1201.56 lakhs, and different types of Mekhela-Chadar and Gamusa are the dominant handloom products in the sample. The highest sales value percentage belongs to Mekhela-Chadar II (34.89%), followed by Gamosa II (19.42%), Gamosa I (16.54%), and Mekhela-Chadar III (15.74%). These four items accounted for 86.59 percent of the total sales volume of the sample. Mekhela Chadar II is valued at Rs 419.25 lakhs, Gamosa II is valued at Rs 233.31 lakhs, Gamosa I is valued at Rs 198.78 lakhs, and Mekhela Chadar III is valued at Rs 189.09 lakhs. The shares of Gamosa III, Dhoti, Cheleng Kapur, shirt, muffler, and tangali are very low.

Pricing Practises

The price strategy is one of the most important components of the marketing mix. According to Kotler & Armstrong (2008), the pricing decision of a product is effected by both internal and external factors such as cost, marketing strategy, organisational consideration, nature of demand, competition, and other environmental elements. Krishnamacharyulu & Ramakrishnan (2011), state that the cost-based approach, the competition-based approach, and the demand-based approach are the three important methods followed by a producer for determining the price of a product. The cost-based pricing strategy determines the overall cost first and then adds the targeted profit. The term “competitive pricing” refers to the process of determining a strategic price for a product or service in order to maximise profit in a given market. According to the competition-based pricing method, the price is set depending on rivals who produce the same products. Under the demand-based pricing method, the producer looks to the needs of the customer’s demand for the product, regardless of price or competition. The majority of handloom enterprises in Assam are run by self-employed microentrepreneurs, and they sell products through different marketing channels. So, the study investigates the methods of price determination adopted by handloom microenterprise units in Assam. Figure 1 shows that more than 75 percent of enterprises adopted cost-based pricing strategies. Again, 13 percent of enterprises set the price of products based on demand. About 9 percent of enterprises fixed the price based on competitor-based methods. Competition-based pricing is like oligopolistic market pricing, where smaller firms follow the leader firm. In the case of handloom enterprises, the micro-weaving units follow the master weavers or large enterprises that produce and sell similar products.

Figure-1 : Handloom Enterprises According to Methods of Price Fixation

Source : Computed from primary data, 2021-22.

Place Practices (Marketing Channels)

The channel of distribution is the important component of placement strategy, which is the third P of marketing mix. Distribution is concerned with the activities involved in bringing the goods from their place of original production to the place of their final consumption. Handloom products of sample enterprises are distributed through different marketing channels. The four marketing channels are revealed in sample handloom enterprises. These four marketing channels are

Channel I : Entrepreneurs → Direct consumer. It can be called zero level channel with no intermediary between producer and consumer.

Channel II : Entrepreneurs → Village Trader → Consumer. It can be called one level channel with one intermediary between producer and consumer.

Channel III : Entrepreneurs → Retailer → Consumer. It can be called one level channel with one intermediary between producer and consumer.

Channel IV : Entrepreneurs → Wholesaler → Retailer → Consumer. It can be called two level channels with two intermediaries between producer and consumer.

Table 3: Marketing Channels of Handloom Micro-enterprises in Assam

Marketing Channel	No. of enterprises	Percentage
Direct consumer (Channel I)	188	60.26
Village trader (Channel II)	212	67.95
Retail shop (Channel III)	29	9.29
Wholesaler (Channel IV)	63	20.19

Source: Computed from primary data, 2021-22

Note: Parentheses indicates percentage of total sample enterprises of each category.

The percentage does not add up to 100 as many respondents sells their product more than one marketing channels.

The handloom microenterprise owner uses their preferred marketing channels based on convenience. An entrepreneur typically uses multiple marketing channels. Table 3 revealed that about 60 percent and 67 percent of enterprises sell their products through channels I and II, respectively. About 20 percent of enterprise sales are through channel IV, and about 9 percent of enterprise sales are through channel III. As per a focus group discussion (FGD) with handloom entrepreneurs, it was observed that marketing channels I and II are more profitable.

Promotional Practices of Sample Handloom Enterprises :

Promotion is one of the most important components of the 4P marketing mix. Producers use the promotion to enlighten consumers about the characteristics and advantages of products and services and to encourage them to buy the products or services. The promotion mix, which includes personal selling, advertising, sales promotion, direct marketing, and public relations, is the primary tool for communicating with customers (Kotler & Keller, 2016). Since handloom is a household-based enterprise, all the enterprises are not adopting any promotional activities for selling their products. But some of the handloom enterprises are adopting promotional methods for selling their products. The enterprises practise promotional activities through advertisement (social media, banner display, etc.), participation in trade fairs and exhibitions, sales representatives, and promotional gifts and special discounts. Figure-2 shows that out of 312 sample enterprises, only 28.53 percent follow at least one type of promotional method.

Figure-2 : Distribution Sample Enterprises According to Adoption of Promotional Practices

Source : Computed from primary data, 2021-22.

Marketing Problems

The PCA has been applied to analyse the key marketing problems of sample handloom enterprises in Assam. The result of KMO is 0.720, which is more than 0.50, and the chi-square value is 1762.77 with 171 degrees of freedom, which is significant at a 1 percent level. It implies that the PCA technique is appropriate for the analysis of the marketing problems of handloom enterprises in Assam.

According to a rule of thumb, factors with Eigen values greater than one are considered principal components (OECD, 2008). The Eigen value indicates the relative importance of each variable. The initial eigenvalues of all components are also shown with the help of the Scree plot in Figure 6.4. Seven factors are identified with an Eigen value greater than one.

The names of the perceived factors and the variance explained by the extracted factors are presented in Tables 6.17. The seven factors are extracted by a rotated component matrix, and these factors together explained 69.63 percent of the variance of the variables. The communality value of each variable is high, and it is greater than 0.5.

The factor I explained was 20.26 percent of the variance and was constituted by four variables, such as lack of exporting facilities, insufficient promotion, high advertisement costs, and lack of marketing support from the government. These

Figure-3 : Eigenvalue of Marketing Problems of Sample Enterprises

Source : Computed from primary data, October-February, 2021-22.

four variables share a common problem in the marketing of handloom enterprises in Assam. Hence, these four variables may be clubbed together and referred to as “promotional variables. Factor II explained 14.27 percent of the variance and is constituted by three variables: the existence of inferior handloom products in the market, a lack of customer awareness about the quality of handloom products, and a lack of marketing information. And these three variables club together and are referred to as lack of customer awareness. Factor III is loaded with three variables: difficulties in timely marketing of products, competition from rival enterprises, and the selling channel. Hence, the common problem reflected by these factors is the challenge from customers, which together accounts for 9.98 percent of variance.

Factor IV was formed by two supply-side variables, such as raw material problems and warehousing facilities, and explained the 7.71 percent variance. Factor V includes three variables: the effect of price fluctuations, a low margin on the selling price, and seasonal demand. So, the common problem reflected by this factor is demand fluctuation. The loaded variables of factor VI are exploitation by intermediaries and changes in fashion. So this factor can be termed “intervention by intermediaries. The last factor, VII, is constituted by two variables: lack of product diversification and accessibility of raw materials. The two variables may be grouped together and termed “lack of product diversity.

Table 4: Perceived Factors of Marketing Problems of Sample Handloom Enterprises

Factors and Variables Name	Factors						
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII
Factor I (Promotional variables)							
Lack of exporting facilities	.730	-.045	.244	.190	-.041	.052	.063
Insufficient promotion	.873	.015	.114	.163	-.011	.067	-.020
High advertisement cost	.756	.011	.221	.012	.078	-.143	-.020
Lack of marketing support from Government	.758	.147	-.038	-.035	-.063	.144	-.123
Factor II (Lack of Customer Awareness)							
Presence of lower quality handloom fabrics in the market	-.025	.750	-.018	-.018	.064	.128	.036
Lack of customer's awareness about the quality of product	.082	.807	.120	.130	.099	-.057	.147
Lack of marketing information	.066	.794	.044	.193	.116	.018	.048
Factor III (Challenges from competitor)							
Difficulties in timely marketing of products	.079	.033	.801	.018	.126	.149	.049
Competition from rival enterprises	.153	.135	.716	-.106	-.059	.208	.023
Selling methods/ channels	.254	-.049	.718	.211	.072	-.063	-.022
Factor IV (Supply side bottleneck)							
Limited supply of yarn by NHDC/SHDC	.127	.047	.072	.883	-.012	-.008	.090
Lack of warehousing	.124	.220	.005	.840	-.074	.088	-.054
Factor V (Demand fluctuation)							
Effect of price fluctuations	.046	.453	.013	-.104	.643	.023	.096
Low margin on selling price	-.066	.010	.214	.170	.812	.023	.121
Seasonal demand	-.001	.106	-.061	-.196	.738	.232	-.041
Factor VI (Intervention by intermediaries)							
Exploitations by intermediaries	.021	-.016	.053	.063	.168	.887	.114
Frequently changes in fashion and demand	.104	.157	.416	.022	.084	.715	-.037
Factor VII (Lack of product diversity)							
Limited product	-.118	.270	-.032	-.102	.117	.123	.681
Raw materials problems	.014	.002	.063	.121	.017	-.019	.859
Variance							
Percentage of Variance	20.26	14.27	9.98	7.71	6.01	5.88	5.52
Cumulative Percentage of Variance	20.26	34.52	44.51	52.21	58.22	64.10	69.62

Source: Computed from primary data, October-February, 2021-22

Note: Loading value above 0.5 are boldfaced

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization

Conclusions

This paper provides a comprehensive discussion of the marketing mix adopted by sample handloom enterprises in Assam. Though the handloom enterprises in Assam produce a variety of product items, there is a need to provide provision for innovative design, brand building, and value addition in handloom fabrics. The majority of enterprises sold their products through direct consumer sales and village traders. Due to the low technology and household-based nature of the handloom industry, a very small proportion of enterprises adopted promotional strategies for selling their products. The majority of handloom enterprises in Assam follow a cost-based pricing approach for fixing the price of the product. Promotional variables, a lack of customer awareness, challenges from competitors, supply-side bottlenecks, demand fluctuation, intervention by intermediaries, and a lack of product diversity are the major marketing challenges facing handloom enterprises in Assam. Policymakers need to establish a government market hub for handloom products, create online marketing channels, low-cost advertisement platforms, etc. for the development of the rural handloom sector.

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